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Effects of activator and catalyst concentration on reaction kinetics and polymer properties in reactive thermoplastic pultrusion of nylon 6

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Motivation

Advantages of reactive anionic polyamide 6

Motivation

Die length and pull-off speed: influence on the polymerization time

In-situ pultrusion line with caprolactam

The polymerization time is determined by the pull-off speed and die length

Matrix dwell time in die

Polymerization times for economical in-situ pultrusion: < 36 s

State of research

Previous ratio regulations

Concentrations of Brüggolen C10 (NaCl) as catalyst and Brüggolen C20P (HDCL) as activator used in T-RTM

[A] : [C] in wt.-%	[A] : [C] in mol.-%	Relative ratio [A] : [C]	Source, year
3,0 : 4,5		1 : 1,5	Thomassey et al. [1], 2017
1,0 : 2,0 - 2,5 : 5,0		1 : 2	Wendel et al. [2], 2018
1,0 : 2,5 - 3,0 : 4,5		1 : 2,5 - 1 : 1,5	Choi et al. [3], 2019
3,2 : 3,2		1 : 1	Osváth et al. [4], 2020
	0,6 : 1,2	1 : 2	Murray et al. [5], 2021
3,0 : 3,0		1 : 1	Semperger et al. [6], 2022
1,5 : 2,2 - 4,0 : 6,0		1 : 1,5	Lagarinhos et al. [7], 2022

No standardized formulation for activator and catalyst concentration or ratio can be defined.

Formulation development

Investigation of polymerization kinetics

Semi-adiabatic beaker tests

Formulation development

Determination of a suitable relative mixing ratio for the in-situ Pultrusion

Relative mixing ratio from activator to catalyst

→ $(\max. d\beta/dt)_{\min. Cat} = [A] : [C] = 1,0 : 2,0 \text{ wt.-%}$

Ratio dependent polymerization kinetics

Gradual increase of the catalyst concentration

Formulation development

Determination of suitable total concentrations

With increasing total concentrations of Act./Cat., the polymerization rate increases disproportionately

Formulations \geq **R6** suitable for pull-off speeds up to **1.5 m/min**

Formulation development

Influence of the activator and catalyst concentration on polymer properties

Influence on the weight-average molar mass

Approx. linear reduction of molar masses through increased proportion of activator and catalyst

Influence on the residual monomer content

Constant low residual monomer content at relevant formulations (\geq R6)

Conclusion

Semi-adiabatic beaker tests are a valid method for investigating the influence of activator and catalyst concentration on kinetics and properties

The catalyst concentration can be limited to a minimum at an optimum ratio of $[A] : [C] = 1.0 : 2.0$ wt.% for max. reaction rate, high polymer properties and less side reactions.

From an activator concentration of 2.75 wt.% and a corresponding catalyst concentration of 5.5 wt.%, economical pultrusion is possible at a pull-off speed of ≥ 1.5 m/min

Increasing the activator and catalyst concentration even further showed no significant negative influence on the investigated polymer properties

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Thanks!

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